

Pioneering AI in MLTC: Bridging Research and Practice

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The
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Focussing on the future:

How do we ensure impact through translation of your research to improve health & social care for MLTC patients, in the next 5 years?

The workshop logistics

The workshop was designed to provide members of the AIM community with an opportunity to discuss key topics shaping the future of AI and MLTC research, aiming to improve lives for those living with or caring for people with Multiple Long-Term Conditions. In collaboration with NIHR, six discussion topics with guiding questions were prepared to explore challenges and potential solutions.

The event welcomed 80-100 registered attendees, with 12-16 participants engaging in discussions on each topic and eight joining online. A one-hour session included 50 minutes for discussion, focusing on capturing attendees' insights and identifying three key takeaways for feedback.

There were 7 topics discussed in the workshop, this summary includes the discussion and takeaway from the 6th topic.

- **Topic 1: How can we mobilise knowledge that has been generated by AIM?**
- **Topic 2: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?**
- **Topic 3: How can we champion early career researchers in MLTC research?**
- **Topic 4: What technical support is needed for the next stage of translation/impact?**
- **Topic 5: Who do we need to engage to ensure broad collaboration for translating research?**
- **Topic 6: How would we move towards system thinking and transdisciplinary research in MLTC?**
- **Topic 7: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?**

Topic 6: How would we move towards system thinking and transdisciplinary research in MLTC?

Context

- **Multidisciplinary research:** is the cooperation of researchers from several different disciplines, but each working in their own context with little cross-fertilization among disciplines, primarily sharing information and results at the end of their research to support the overall combined findings.

- **Interdisciplinary research:** in contrast involves a much closer interaction, including transferring methods and knowledge between the academic disciplines (sometimes in turn leading to

the development of what are eventually considered new academic disciplines, with their own characteristic knowledge, approaches, and boundaries to other disciplines)

- The main difference between research questions in interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary research is that interdisciplinary research involves collaboration across disciplines, while multidisciplinary research involves independent work by different disciplines.
- **What distinguishes transdisciplinary?**
 - There are multiple forms/modes and definitions for transdisciplinary but the common themes are:
 - It is used to tackle **wicked, complex** problems
 - It tries to transcend disciplinary boundaries and knowledge systems.
 - The involvement of (non-academic) societal actors as process participants, so, stakeholder engagement is essential part of the method from the very beginning;
 - It usually creates **actionable knowledge** or intervention;
 - Slides from the AIM RSF Seminar: <https://zenodo.org/records/13168572>

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The key takeaways

1. The key point is that MLTC is a 'wicked problem' which requires a transdisciplinary approach, rather than an interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary one.
2. Working in a transdisciplinary way is challenging and evolves over a long period. This means it calls for completely different funding models and incentive structures.

Recommendations for MLTC funders

1. Change dramatically the funding and evaluation structures:
 - Implement longer funding cycles (5+ years minimum) to enable relationship-building
 - Create multi-stage funding models starting with development awards
 - Establish dedicated funding for team-building activities and workshops
 - Develop new metrics that assess collaboration quality, not just quantity
 - Support distributed leadership models
 - Fund 'transdisciplinary research units' for long-term impact
2. Build supportive research ecosystems:
 - Fund training programmes for PhD students and ECRs around inter/transdisciplinary
 - Create transdisciplinary summer schools and workshops
 - Develop safe spaces for sharing lived experiences
 - Fund mentorship programmes across disciplines
 - Create career progression pathways that value transdisciplinary skills because the current mode discourage transdisciplinary
 - Enable long-term evolution of transdisciplinary collaborations

Summary of all the discussion

- **Challenges of Achieving Transdisciplinary Work:**
 - Participants noted that MLTC needs a transdisciplinary approach but true transdisciplinary work is rare and difficult to achieve due to ingrained academic cultures.
 - There's a tension between the funders' desire for transdisciplinary research and the incentive structures that reward specialisation and individual achievement.

- The competitive nature of academia was highlighted as a significant barrier.
- Openness to different perspectives and a willingness to change one's identity from a discipline expert to a team member were highlighted.
 - The ability to constantly learn and engage in conversations with people from different fields was seen as a key skill.
- Tension Between Specialisation and Transdisciplinary Approaches:
 - Participants discussed an "hourglass model" where researchers specialise deeply before broadening out again.
 - The challenge of asking PhD students to become both specialists and generalists was noted.
 - Power Dynamics
 - The discussion touched on the power imbalances inherent in academic hierarchies, particularly for PhD students with multiple supervisors.
 - An anecdote was shared about researchers with multiple long-term conditions feeling unable to disclose their status, highlighting broader societal biases.
 - The discussion acknowledged the inherent tension between the competitive nature of academia and the collaborative requirements of transdisciplinary work.
 - Participants suggested that while competitiveness can't be eliminated, the rules and incentives can be changed to promote collaboration in certain contexts.
- **Importance of trust-building and long-term Relationships when developing inter/trans approach:**
 - The MELD-B project was cited as an example where trust has developed over time, leading to more effective collaboration.
 - One participant noted, "We had a development award before the main award, and we sort of came through that and developed a bigger team."
 - The value of continuity in teams was emphasised, with concerns raised about losing established relationships when moving to new projects.
- **PhD Students and Interdisciplinary work:**
 - Several PhD students shared experiences of having supervisors from different disciplines, noting both benefits and challenges.
 - One student mentioned, "We often attend meetings, and we wouldn't necessarily agree, because between the two disciplines and so you are a bit sat in the middle."

- The stress and frustration of navigating conflicting advice from supervisors in different disciplines was acknowledged.
- **Evaluation of Transdisciplinary work:**
 - Participants called for new ways of evaluating transdisciplinary research that focus on the process as well as outcomes.
 - One participant noted, "The impact isn't the journey as well as the destination. And what do we so we need to learn about actually, how is the way that we work together to promote transdisciplinary groups?"
- **Distributed leadership models:**
 - The MELD-B project was cited as an example of distributed leadership in practice.
 - However, it was noted that grant application processes still often require a single Principal Investigator, creating tension with the reality of interdisciplinary work.
- **Language & communication:**
 - Participants noted the challenge of different disciplines using different terminology for similar concepts.
 - One participant shared, "We often attend meetings, and we wouldn't necessarily agree, because between the two disciplines and so you are a bit sat in the middle."
- **Time and resource allocation:**
 - The need for more time in interdisciplinary projects was emphasised. As one participant put it, "Big, it takes longer, but you get to something that's better in the end."
 - The importance of allocating resources for team-building and mutual understanding was stressed.
- **Systemic changes:**
 - Participants called for changes to the broader academic system, including how research is funded and how success is measured.
 - One participant suggested looking at alternative funding models, noting that "there are countries who allocate funding randomly."
- **Training and skill development:**
 - The need for specific training in interdisciplinary collaboration was discussed, with one participant mentioning an upcoming workshop on effective collaborations across disciplines.
 - It was noted that while experience is crucial, there are also specific skills that can be developed and trained.